

Morbidity and Mortality Associated With Abdominal Hysterectomy

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ABSTRACT

Objective: This study was done to determine morbidity and mortality associated with abdominal hysterectomy.

Study Design: This is an observational study.

Duration and Setting: This study was started in June 2017 and completed in December 2017, comprising on 7 months duration. Study was conducted in Chaudhary Akram Teaching Hospital Lahore, Pkistan.

Patients and Methods: Total 96 patients were included in this study which were operated for abdominal hysterectomy in the hospital during given period of seven months. These cases were admitted in the Gynaecology and obstetrics ward due to various causes such as DUB, leomyoma uterine and endometrial hyperplasia etc. These patients were admitted in the ward on OPD bases. Proper investigations and preoperative workup was done. Anesthesia fitness was taken. Cardiology opinion was also taken in ladies above 45 years for any cardiac problem. CBC, serum profile, chest x-ray, PT, INR, ECG were done. These patients were planned for abdominal hysterectomy. Most of them underwent total hysterectomy while few had sub-total hysterectomy. Consent was also taken from the incharge of ward for conducting study. Proper history was taken from all paytients, physical examination done and findings were documented as well. All data was analyzed in Microsoft office version 2007 and SPSS software. Results were calculated in the form of frequencies and they were presented as tables, charts and graphs.

Results: There were 96 cases in the study. Age of patients was in the range of 30-55 years with mean age of 46.7 years. Most of the cases were having age above 40 years. There were 13(13.5%) with age 30-35 years, 20(20.8%) cases 36-40 years, 25(26.1%) having age 41-45 years, 28(29.2%) cases with age 46-50 years and 10 cases were in age group above 50 years. There were various causes of hysterectomy out of which dysfunctional uterine bleeding was most common in 38(39.6%), leomyoma uterine in 20(20.8%), endometrial hyperplasia in 9(9.3%), adenomyosis in 14(14.6%), Pelvic tumor or ovarian cyst in 7(7.3%) and endometriosis was found cause in 3(3.1%) cases. After operation patients were retained in the ward and full monitoring was done. Complications were observed and documented. In 5(5.2%) cases intra-operative hemorrhage occurred, bladder injury in 2(2.1%), ureteric injury happened in 1 case, perforation of bowel occurred in 3(3.12%), post operative hematoma formation in 2(2.1%), enterocutaneous fistula in 2(2.1%), DVT formation in one case and relaprotomy was done in one case. Total abdominal hysterectomy was done in 90(93.7%) and subtotal hysterectomy was done in 6(6.3%) cases.

Conclusion: Abdominal hysterectomy is associated with high rate of complications. Intraoperative hemorrhage is most common complication. Most common cause of hysterectomy was DUB. Complications were higher in old age females.

Key Words: abdominal hysterectomy, morbidity, mortality

INTRODUCTION

Hysterectomy is usually performed in gynecological wards via abdominal approach or vaginal approach. According to a report about 0.5 million hysterectomies are performed each year in America and about one hundred thousand in UK.^{1,2} It is also most commonly performed gynecological operation in Pakistan. Its indications are dysfunctional uterine bleeding, leomyoma, adenomyosis, ovarian cyst and endometriosis. These causes are more common in old age females. Initially DUB is treated with medicines and when medical treatment does not cure it then surgery is performed. Hysterectomy is done either total hysterectomy or subtotal hysterectomy depending upon the indication and age of female.³ Total ninety six patients were included in this study which were operated for abdominal hysterectomy in the hospital during given period of seven months. These cases were admitted in the Gynaecology and obstetrics ward due to various causes such as DUB, leomyoma uterine and endometrial hyperplasia etc. These patients were admitted in the ward on OPD bases. Proper investigations and preoperative workup was done. Anesthesia fitness was taken. Cardiology opinion was also taken in ladies above 45 years for any cardiac problem. . It is also most commonly performed gynecological operation in Pakistan. Its indications are dysfunctional uterine bleeding, leomyoma, adenomyosis, ovarian cyst and endometriosis.⁴ These causes are more common in old age females. Initially DUB is treated with medicines and when medical treatment does not cure it then surgery is performed. Hysterectomy is done either total hysterectomy or subtotal hysterectomy depending upon the indication and age of female. There are many complications associated with this operation. Most common complication is hemorrhage during performing surgery or post operative hematoma development which may indicate re exploration and hemostasis. Such patients present with anemia, dyspnea and abdominal pain and distension with low blood pressure soon after the operation. Other complications include wound infection and perforation of intestine which is also very common in surgical practice and in this condition general

surgeon should be called for repairing intestine. Fecal spillage may cause peritonitis of severe type and if untreated patient may die with sepsis. There are many complications associated with this operation. Most common complication is hemorrhage during performing surgery or post operative hematoma development which may indicate re exploration and hemostasis. Such patients present with anemia, dyspnea and abdominal pain and distension with low blood pressure soon after the operation.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

This is a prospective type of study which was started in June 2017 and completed in December 2017 comprising on seven months duration. It was conducted in gynecology ward of a teaching hospital. A criterion was defined for selection of patients and which patients were falling to the criteria they were included in the study and rest of the patients was excluded. Which patients did not give consent or refused for surgery, discharged against doctor advice after operation and did not stay in the ward for required period of time of at least 3 days post operatively, they all were not included in the study. Total 96 patients were included in this study which were operated for abdominal hysterectomy in the hospital during given period of seven months. Total ninety six patients were included in this study which were operated for abdominal hysterectomy in the hospital during given period of seven months. These cases were admitted in the Gynaecology and obstetrics ward due to various causes such as DUB, leomyoma uterine and endometrial hyperplasia etc. These patients were admitted in the ward on OPD bases. Proper investigations and preoperative workup was done. These cases were admitted in the Gynaecology and obstetrics ward due to various causes such as DUB, leomyoma uterine and endometrial hyperplasia etc. These patients were admitted in the ward on OPD bases. Proper investigations and preoperative workup was done. Anesthesia fitness was taken. Cardiology opinion was also taken in ladies above 45 years for any cardiac problem. CBC, serum profile, chest x-ray, PT, INR, ECG were done. These patients were planned for abdominal hysterectomy. Most of them underwent total hysterectomy while few had sub-total hysterectomy. Consent was also taken from the incharge of ward for conducting study. Proper history was taken from all patients, physical examination done and findings were documented as well. All data was analyzed in Microsoft office version 2007 and SPSS software.

Results were calculated in the form of frequencies and they were presented as tables, charts and graphs.

RESULTS

There were 96 cases in the study. Age of patients was in the range of 30-55 years with mean age of 46.7 years. Most of the cases were having age above 40 years. There were 13(13.5%) with age 30-35 years, 20(20.8%) cases 36-40 years, 25(26.1%) having age 41-45 years, 28(29.2%) cases with age 46-50 years and 10 cases were in age group above 50 years. There were various causes of hysterectomy out of which dysfunctional uterine bleeding was most common in 38(39.6%), leomyoma uterine in 20(20.8%), endometrial hyperplasia in 9(9.3%), adenomyosis in 14(14.6%), Pelvic tumor or ovarian cyst in 7(7.3%) and endometriosis was found cause in 3(3.1%) cases. After operation patients were retained in the ward and full monitoring was done. Complications were observed and documented. These causes are more common in old age females. Initially DUB is treated with medicines and when medical treatment does not cure it then surgery is performed. Hysterectomy is done either total hysterectomy or subtotal hysterectomy depending upon the indication and age of female. Total ninety six patients were included in this study which were operated for abdominal hysterectomy in the hospital during given period of seven months. In 5(5.2%) cases intra-operative hemorrhage occurred, bladder injury in 2(2.1%), ureteric injury happened in 1 case, perforation of bowel occurred in 3(3.12%), post operative hematoma formation in 2(2.1%), enterocutaneous fistula in 2(2.1%), DVT formation in one case and relaprotomy was done in one case. Total abdominal hysterectomy was done in 90(93.7%) and subtotal hysterectomy was done in 6(6.3%) cases. During this period of seven months only 2 cases died after hysterectomy due to sepsis. So mortality was low in this regard.

(Figure-1) Frequency of total and subtotal abdominal hysterectomy

(Figure-2) indications of hysterectomy among females in study group

(Table-1) Number of patients in different age groups

Age of patients (years)	Number of Patients (n)	(%)
30-35	13	13.15
36-40	20	20.8
41-45	25	26.1
46-50	28	29.2
Above 50	10	10.4
Total	96	100

(Table-2) Complication due to hysterectomy among 96 females of study group

Complications of Hysterectomy	Number of patients (n)	(%)
Hemorrhage during operation	5	5.2
Ureter injury	1	1.1
Bladder injury	2	2.1
Intestinal perforation	3	3.12
Hematoma	2	2.1
Fistula	4	4.2
Re exploration	2	2.1
DVT	1	1.1
Wound infection	4	4.2
Total	21	100

DISCUSSION

Many females experience different types of genecological problems among which most common is dysfunctional uterine bleeding

unresponsive to medical therapy.⁵ It is more common in old age females usually over 45 years and in this condition surgery is indicated. Hysterectomy is usually performed in gynecological wards via abdominal approach or vaginal approach. According to a report about 0.5 million hysterectomies are performed each year in America and about one hundred thousand in UK. It is also most commonly performed gynecological operation in Pakistan.⁶ Its indications are dysfunctional uterine bleeding, leomyoma, adenomyosis, ovarian cyst and endometriosis. These causes are more common in old age females. Initially DUB is treated with medicines and when medical treatment does not cure it then surgery is performed. Hysterectomy is done either total hysterectomy or subtotal hysterectomy depending upon the indication and age of female.⁷ Total ninety six patients were included in this study which were operated for abdominal hysterectomy in the hospital during given period of seven months. This is a prospective type of study which was started in June 2017 and completed in December 2017 comprising on seven months duration. It was conducted in gynecology ward of a teaching hospital.⁸ A criterion was defined for selection of patients and which patients were falling to the criteria they were included in the study and rest of the patients was excluded. Which patients did not give consent or refused for surgery, discharged against doctor advice after operation and did not stay in the ward for required period of time of at least 3 days post operatively, they all were not included in

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in 3(3.1%) cases. After operation patients were retained in the ward and full monitoring was done. Complications were observed and documented. These causes are more common in old age females. Initially DUB is treated with medicines and when medical treatment does not cure it then surgery is performed.¹¹ Many studies have been done in this aspect in different countries of the world but very little work has been done in Pakistan and much data is lacking related to complications post operatively. So this study was conducted to collect data related to it.

Conclusion

Hysterectomy is a most commonly performed operation in gynecology wards worldwide. Abdominal hysterectomy is associated with high rate of complications. Intraoperative hemorrhage is most common complication. Most common cause of hysterectomy was DUB. Complications were higher in old age females. Complications can be reduced by making operative techniques more advance such as use of laparoscope which is minimal invasive method with no scar or abdominal incision. Hysterectomy should not be performed in simple cases and medical treatment should always be used first followed by surgery if medical treatment does not improve condition.

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